

RERAM

research to innovation in
resource efficiency

EU FP7 project no. 609573
01/06/2014-31/05/2016
www.reram.eu

R2I

Research-to-Innovation Dialogues for Resource Efficiency

Promoting a partnership of industries, research and authorities
to foster efficient use of raw materials and a more competitive
forestry and wood manufacturing sector

July 2016

Wald-Zentrum

Impressum

Citation

Kies U., Oberwimmer R., Vorobey V., 2016.
R2I Research-to-Innovation Dialogues. RERAM project report
D4.2. Internationales Institut für Wald und Holz e.V.,
Holzcluster Steiermark GmbH, Wood Processing and Furniture
Cluster. Münster, Graz, Lviv. www.reram.eu

Deliverable no.

D4.2

Dissemination level

Public

Lead beneficiary

HCS - Holzcluster Steiermark GmbH

Authors

Uwe Kies (IIWH), Roland Oberwimmer (HCS),
Volodymyr Vorobey (WPFC)

Approved by

Andreas Schulte (IIWH, lead coordinator)

Date, version

18/07/2016, final version

IIWH - Internationales Institut für Wald und Holz e.V.
Hafenweg 24a, 48155 Münster, Germany
uwe.kies@wald-zentrum.de | www.wald-zentrum.de

HCS - Holzcluster Steiermark GmbH
Holzinnovationszentrum 1a, 8740 Zeltweg, Austria
oberwimmer@holzcluster-steiermark.at
www.holzcluster-steiermark.at

DOMV - WPFC Wood and Furniture Processing Cluster
Henerala Chuprynyky 50, 12, 79044 Lviv, Ukraine
vv@ppv.net.ua | www.domv.lviv.ua

The RERAM project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme (FP7 2007-2013) under the grant agreement n°609573 from 01/06/2014 to 31/05/2016. The content of the document reflects only the authors' views. The European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Table of contents

1.	Objectives.....	5
2.	Report on Activities and Achievements.....	5
2.1	Overview of accomplished R2I events and meetings	5
2.2	R2I Dialogue events in 2014.....	9
2.2.1	INCONET EU-EaP STI conference.....	9
2.2.2	R2I Med + EaP Cluster Meeting.....	10
2.2.3	Eastern Economic Congress in Białystok, Poland.....	11
2.2.4	Conference “Usage of forest resources in Poland”	13
2.2.5	Cooperation for the Future: professionals’ meeting of wood construction and wood-based material producers	14
2.2.6	ERA-NET SUMFOREST EU-Russia Workshop	15
2.2.7	9 th ILN Workshop ‘International cooperation in Horizon 2020’	16
2.2.8	Kick-off meeting of FUNES Project	17
2.2.9	ener2i Brokerage event	18
2.2.10	Meeting with representatives of the Ministry of the Environment and General Directorate of State Forests	19
2.3	R2I Dialogue events in 2015.....	20
2.3.1	RERAM Roundtable Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine	20
2.3.2	Business meeting “International Contact Days” in Ukraine.....	21
2.3.3	Eastern Partnership Panel on Research and Innovation.....	22
2.3.4	RERAM Roundtable Lviv, Ukraine	23
2.3.5	RERAM Roundtable Rivne, Ukraine.....	24
2.3.6	AFET-ITRE Conference ‘Building together a knowledge-oriented and forward-looking EU Neighbourhood’ in the European Parliament.....	25
2.3.7	Joint UNECE-FAO/RERAM Event ‘Capacity building for Sustainable Forest Management and Resource Efficiency in the Caucasus and Central Asia’	26
2.3.8	1 st Meeting of Furniture Industry Clusters of Greater Poland	28
2.3.9	National stakeholder roundtable organised by the Ukrainian Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources	29
2.3.10	Roundtable ‘Action Plan for Lviv Regional Forestry Administration’	30
2.3.11	Lisderevmash – National Ukrainian Wood Industry Fair: Innovation workshop at the Wood Invest Forum 2015	31
2.3.12	Seminar Clusterisation and Innovations in the Republic of Moldova.....	32
2.3.13	TEEB study for Georgian forest sector: stakeholder meeting.....	33
2.3.14	UNECE/FAO-UNDA Balkan workshop on Forest Products Markets and Forest Sector Workforce	34
2.3.15	Eastern Partnership R2I Cluster Meeting.....	35
2.3.16	Lviv Wood Processing and Furniture Cluster Forum	36

2.4	R2I Dialogue events in 2016.....	37
2.4.1	Eastern Partnership Panel on Environment and Climate Change.....	37
2.4.2	Georgia National Forestry Agency Strategy: Stakeholder Workshop	37
2.4.3	Study trip for Ukrainian wood enterprises to Austria	38
2.4.4	Parliament of Georgia, Environmental Protection and Natural Resources Committee, Working Meeting about the Forest Code	39
2.4.5	LUKE Symposium on Wood Products Industries in Future Bioeconomy Business	40
2.4.6	RERAM Resource Efficiency Workshop & Training in Georgia.....	41
2.4.7	UNIDO RECP Trainings for national experts in Georgia	42
2.4.8	RERAM conference in Georgia ‘Efficient and sustainable use of resources in forestry sector’	43
2.4.9	RERAM Final Conference in Lviv, Ukraine	44
2.4.10	Eastern Partnership Panel on Environment and Climate Change.....	45
2.4.11	RECC side event at the UNECE 8 th Ministerial Conference in Batumi.....	46
3.	Annex: Agendas and Participants Lists	48

1. Objectives

This deliverable D4.2 is a summary report of the RERAM project WP4 outreach activities targeting wood industries and further stakeholders in the ENP countries. The **Task 4.2** comprises *Research-to-Innovation (R2I) Dialogues*, which include moderated roundtables, workshops and conferences engaging multiple stakeholders in the regional triple helix, including business, research and authorities. The purpose is to initiate a dialogue on country level between important stakeholders on the topic of resource efficiency in the wood value added chain. The R2I Dialogues facilitated exchange on the topic to promote more cluster collaborations and policy dialogues, which can foster broader engagement of the target group and further market uptake of the enterprise checks, trainings and resource efficiency solutions for SMEs developed by the project. The objectives of Task 4.2 include:

- To inform triple helix partners about the results of WP2 & WP3 and the implications on the national forest-based sector
- To provide benchmark data on resource efficiency and use of raw materials by country and by processing stage
- To guide a discussion on regional to national strategies in resource efficiency and material use and to reach a consensus on this topic of triple helix partners
- To outline the identified regional demand for research and technical development and to define top priorities and areas for further joint projects

This final report D4.2 documents the complete work conducted during the periods 1 and 2 between 01/06/2014 to 31/05/2016.

2. Report on Activities and Achievements

2.1 Overview of accomplished R2I events and meetings

A total of **37 R2I events and meetings** have been conducted as part of the RERAM action. These include events organized and hosted by RERAM beneficiaries and also events of third parties, e.g. other R2I consortia, RTD institutions, the EC or other international organizations, in which RERAM representatives have participated.

The events had a major dissemination function for the RERAM project and its members, enhancing their visibility and networking in the ENP region towards other RTD initiatives and organizations both on the national and international level. The events covered various target groups of the cluster triple helix, first and foremost SMEs in the forest-based sector, but also other stakeholders, such as administrations, scientists, policy-makers, NGOs, consultants, donor agencies, and the press. The dialogues initiated various impulses for follow-up research, industry and policy development initiatives in the ENP region.

Table 1 List of conducted R2I Dialogue events

No.	Date	Venue	Type	Organizer	Title, main topics of meeting
2014					
1	15-16/05/2014	Yerevan, Armenia	Conference	INCONET EaP	EU-EaP STI conference
<i>Official project start 01/06/2014</i>					
2	05/06/2014	Brussels, Belgium	Meeting	European Commission	R2I Med+EaP Cluster meeting
3	18-19/09/2014	Bialstok, Poland	Congress	PTWP Group	Eastern Economic Congress
4	25/09/2014	Polańczyk, Poland	Conference	AFWT	Conference "Usage of forest resources in Poland"
5	14/10/2014	Poznan, Poland	Meeting	ITD, PPLA, WHA, PWDA	Professionals' meeting of wood construction and wood-based material producers
6	19/11/2014	Kazan, Russia	Conference	ERA-NET SUMFOREST (FP7)	SUMFOREST EU-Russia Workshop, side event at 72 nd session of the UNECE Committee on Forests and the Forest Industry (COFFI)
7	27-28/11/2014	Brussels, Belgium	Workshop	European Commission	9 th ILN - International Learning Network Workshop
8	3-4/12/2014	Paterna, Spain	Meeting	AIDIMA	FUNES project kickoff meeting
9	10-11/12/2014	Chisinau, Moldova	Conference	ener2i consortium	ener2i Brokerage Event in Moldova
10	13/11/2014	Warsaw, Poland	Meeting	MEDFNC	Meeting with Ministry of the Environment
2015					
11	24/03/2015	Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine	Round-table	WPFC	Shortage of raw materials and resources and low competitiveness of wood products
12	26/03/2015	Uzhorod, Ukraine	Meeting	TCCI	Business meeting "International Contact Days" in Ukraine
13	26/03/2015	Brussels, Belgium	Meeting	European Commission	Eastern Partnership Panel on Research and Innovation
14	30/03/2015	Lviv, Ukraine	Round-table	WPFC	Skills development, access to finance and monitoring needs for raw material use
15	31/03/2015	Rivne, Ukraine	Round-table	WPFC	Barriers for forest-based products; opportunities for wood biomass energy chains

No.	Date	Venue	Type	Organizer	Title, main topics of meeting
16	31/03/2015	Brussels, Belgium	Conference	European Commission	AFET-ITRE Conference 'Building together a knowledge-oriented and forward-looking EU Neighbourhood'
17	23/04/2015	Tbilisi, Georgia	Conference	IIWH, UNECE-FAO, RECC	Joint UNECE-FAO/RERAM Event 'Capacity building for Sustainable Forest Management and Resource Efficiency in the Caucasus and Central Asia'
18	29/04/2015	Poznan, Poland	Meeting	GPCC	1 st Meeting of Furniture Clusters of Greater Poland
19	26/05/2015	Kiev, Ukraine	Roundtable	UA MANR	National stakeholder roundtable by the UA MANR
20	28/08/2015	Lviv, Ukraine	Roundtable	WPFC, UNFU	Action Plan for Lviv Regional Forestry Administration
21	23/09/2015	Kiyv, Ukraine	Workshop	WPFC, UNFU	Lisderevmash Wood Industry Fair, Innovation workshop
22	26/11/2015	Chisinau, Moldova	Seminar	AITT	Clusterisation and innovations in the Republic of Moldova
23	26-29/11/2015	Tbilisi, Georgia	Meeting	ENPI FLEG	TEEB study for Georgian forest sector: stakeholder meeting
24	8-10/12/2015	Podgorica, Montenegro	Workshop	UNECE-FAO	UNECE-FAO Balkan workshop on Forest Products Markets and Forest Sector Workforce
25	17/12/2015	Brussels, Belgium	Meeting	European Commission	Eastern Partnership R2I Cluster
26	23/12/2015	Lviv, Ukraine	Forum	WPFC, UNFU	Lviv Wood Processing and Furniture Cluster Forum
2016					
27	16/02/2016	Brussels, Belgium	Meeting	European Commission	Eastern Partnership Panel on Environment & Climate Change
28	27-29/02/2016	Kobuleti, Georgia	Workshop	CENN, GIZ	Georgia National Forestry Agency Strategy: Stakeholders
29	14-18/03/2016	Graz, Austria	Study trip	HCS, FORZA	Study trip for ENP wood enterprises to Styria, Austria
30	24/04/2016	Tbilisi, Georgia	Meeting	PG-EPNRC	Parliament of Georgia, EPNR Committee, Forest Code
31	07-08/04/2016	Lahti, Finland	Conference	LUKE	Symposium on Wood Products Industries in Future Bioeconomy
32	19-20/04/2016	Tbilisi, Georgia	Workshop	RECC, AUG, HCS	Resource efficiency workshop for Georgian companies

No.	Date	Venue	Type	Organizer	Title, main topics of meeting
33	26-27/04/ 2016	Tbilisi, Georgia	Meeting	EEC, UNIDO	UNIDO RECP Trainings for national experts in Georgia
34	06/05/ 2016	Tbilisi, Georgia	Confer- ence	AUG, RECC	RERAM conference in Georgia
35	18-19/05/ 2061	Lviv, Ukraine	Confer- ence	RERAM consortium	RERAM Final Conference
36	26/05/ 2016	Brussels, Belgium	Meeting	European Commission	Eastern Partnership Panel on Environment & Climate Change
<i>Official project end 31/05/2016</i>					
37	09/06/ 2016	Batumi, Georgia	Confer- ence	RECC, AUG	RECC Side Event at UNECE 8 th Ministerial Conference

2.2 R2I Dialogue events in 2014

2.2.1 INCONET EU-EaP STI conference

Note: The conference took place before the official start of RERAM. It presented nevertheless a good first platform to present the project to various ENP stakeholders and establish contacts to various EU-EaP projects.

Date, venue, host, website

15-16/05/2014, Yerevan, Armenia
National Academy of Sciences of Armenia
<http://www.inco-eap.net/en/399.php>

Participants

Over 100 participants; around 60 policy makers, scientific community from EU and EaP countries; around 50 stakeholders from Armenia, among them various international organisations, like Austrian Red Cross, UNDP, Regional Environmental Centre for the Caucasus, Climate East Project, many other Climate Change projects.

RERAM representatives: WPFC (K. Kravchuk); FORZA NGO (Y. Derbal)

Main topics and outcomes

The focus of the Conference was on the EU-EaP STI cooperation in addressing the Societal Challenge of Climate Change. It provided an overview of the international policies, initiatives and programmes targeting the region. It also brought together a good number of best practice examples of projects from the region with the aim to create synergies among them and exploit the potential for future cooperation in H2020.

RERAM was presented by Mrs. Kravchuk > Presentation #11

http://www.inco-eap.net/media/11_RERAM.pdf

Mr. Yury Derbal of FORZA NGO presented the project LOC-CLIM-ACT, > Presentation #13

http://www.inco-eap.net/media/13_LOC_CLIM_ACT.pdf

2.2.2 R2I Med + EaP Cluster Meeting

Date, venue, host, website

05/06/2014, European Commission, Covent Garden 2, Place Rogier 16, Brussels, Belgium

Participants

FP7-INCO R2I project coordinators

RERAM representative: IIWH (U. Kies)

Main topics and outcomes

- STI Policy Developments in EaP and Med
- Synergies among R2I projects and international support actions
- Improvements for support to R2I
- RERAM presentation

2.2.3 Eastern Economic Congress in Białystok, Poland

Date, venue, host, website

18-19/09/2014, Białystok, Poland

PTWP Group

<http://www.wschodnikongres.eu/en/>

Participants

About thousand guests, including regional, Polish and European politicians, leaders of economic life, representatives of Polish and foreign enterprises, experts, and scientists.

Main topics and outcomes

Agenda: <http://www.wschodnikongres.eu/2014/en/agenda/111/>

The Congress has proved a very successful undertaking, which has been confirmed by the attendance of prominent Guests and the acclaim of its Participants, but first of all, by a set of interesting conclusions and recommendations. The event received widespread and positive media coverage of considerable importance to the promotion of investment attractiveness of the eastern regions of Poland. The main topics and results of the Congress were:

- The situation beyond the eastern border of the EU: How does it determine the actions in the field of the economy? How can one pursue economic activity regardless of limitations? Where to look for possibilities and how to modify the plans to date?;
- The policy of the European Union towards Poland's eastern neighbours and its influence on the economy of Eastern Poland. Economic cooperation and common international projects – the role of the EU and the countries outside the European Union. Risks for the EU Member States versus the tendency towards integration and common actions, including the sphere of the economy. Energy security of the countries of Eastern Europe versus the relations with Russia;
- Polish border – the EU border: Is it an open gate or an impenetrable barrier? An assessment of the current situation in border traffic. Border infrastructure – its condition, development and possibilities of modernisation and streamlining. Experience in the development of borderland regions. The European Union and the borderland regions. What type of cooperation does Brussels advocate in the years 2014–2020? Contacts between local governments and state administration. Twin towns in the close neighbourhood;
- The new EU financial framework – seven years of new opportunities. Where are we heading? What investments do we need? Infrastructure development. Pro-development projects: Go for innovations! Investment attractiveness of the eastern macro-region;
- Current challenges for business entities (manufacturers, investors and exporters) related to the geopolitical situation and macroeconomic factors. New markets – an area of potential expansion. Necessary adjustment actions in the traditional markets of

Eastern Europe. Risk management, business in a dynamic situation, forecasting, and flexibility. Barriers to the development of entrepreneurship – the opportunities for eliminating them

Information about RERAM Project was prepared for Minister Grażyna Hencklewska (Ministry of Economy) to be used during her speech about the business relations between Poland and Eastern Countries (information prepared by WTI - attachment 1).

Impressions

Source: wo24.pl

Source: www.bialystokonline.pl

Source: www.archiwalny.miastoryn.pl

Source: www.parp.gov.pl

2.2.4 Conference “Usage of forest resources in Poland”

Date, venue, host, website

25/09/2014, Polańczyk, Poland

Association of Forests and Wood Technologists

<http://www.sitlid.pl/>, www.zsllesko.pl

Participants

About 180 representatives of the forestry-wood sector (mostly scientists, producers, students, authorities) participated in the conference. The conference was addressed to a wide group of people interested in the usage of forest resources, in particular to the representatives of the State Forests and other forest owners and managers, people executing forest management plans, various institutions within the wood sector, local governments, non-governmental organizations, universities and research institutes.

RERAM representative: ITD / Prof. dr. hab. Ewa Ratajczak

Main topics and outcomes

The objective of the Scientific and Technology Conference was to present the issues concerning the current and future usage of forest resources in Poland, as well as a broad discussion and exchange of researchers' and practitioners' opinions on this subject. The conference covered a wide spectrum of issues concerning management of forest resources, in particular the timber harvest volume adjustment.

RERAM project was presented by Prof. Ewa Ratajczak (ITD).

2.2.5 Cooperation for the Future: professionals' meeting of wood construction and wood-based material producers

Date, venue, host, website

14/10/2014, Poznań, Poland

Wood Technology Institute

<http://www.itd.poznan.pl/en/>

Participants

About 80 representatives of industry and sciences (mostly Polish companies connected with the production of wooden construction products).

ITD, co-organised in co-operation with the Polish Parquet Layers Association, Wooden House Association and the Polish Windows and Doors Association.

RERAM representative: ITD / Gabriela Bidzińska

Main topics and outcomes

During the first part of the meeting, the representatives of Institute's various research departments presented their offer of tests and services for the sawmilling, wooden floor material, wooden houses, and builder's carpentry and joinery industries.

In the second part of the meeting, the participants were introduced to the basics of the HORIZON 2020 programme, with special emphasis placed on the financing possibilities of projects executed by both scientific institutions and entrepreneurs.

A delegate of the Association of Polish Parquet Makers and the representatives of POZBUD Company shared with the audience their experience in implementation of projects funded by the European Commission.

In addition at the end of the meeting a representative of the Greater Poland Quality Institute gave her presentation on advisory and consulting offer of her institution as the support for the development of wood processing industry companies [Source: ITD].

RERAM was presented by Gabriela Bidzińska (ITD).

2.2.6 ERA-NET SUMFOREST EU-Russia Workshop

Date, venue, host, website

19/11/2014, Hotel Korston, Kazan, Russian Federation

ERA-NET SUMFOREST Consortium

Official side event to the 72nd session of the

UNECE Committee on Forests and the Forest Industry (COFFI)

in Kazan from 18-21 November 2014

<https://www.sumforest.org/>

Participants

High-level representatives of the forest sector in Russia and Eastern Partnership, representatives of applied research, academic and educational organisations, sectoral ministries and representatives of research funding organisations, as well as SUMFOREST partners - owners of forest research programmes in EU Countries

RERAM representative: AUG (Prof. Teimuraz Kandelaki)

Main topics and outcomes

EU-Russia workshop 'Sustainable forest management - research capacities and priorities' organized in the frame of the EU-Russia Year of Science by the ERA-NET SUMFOREST consortium. The objective was to discuss and share views on potentials to increase cooperation and setting joint priorities in research needs in the field of sustainable forest management in EU and Russia and the Eastern partnership (EaP) countries.

SUMFOREST workshop agenda - including links to all presentations

https://www.sumforest.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/11/WP6-Kazan-workshop_programme_ENG.pdf

Georgia presentation by RERAM partner Prof. Teimuraz Kandelaki of AUG

https://www.sumforest.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/11/Kandelaki_Kazan.pdf

2.2.7 9th ILN Workshop 'International cooperation in Horizon 2020'

Date, venue, host, website

27-28/11/2014

The Hotel, Boulevard de Waterloo 38, Brussels, Belgium

ILN team: APRE, Help Forward, EUROPAMEDA, on behalf of the European Commission

www.ilnworld.eu

Participants

ILN Network members, FP7-INCO R2I project coordinators

RERAM representative: IWH (U. Kies)

Main topics and outcomes

The International Learning Network (ILN) workshop "International cooperation in Horizon 2020" informed on recent issues related to bi-regional and bi-lateral international cooperation in Horizon 2020 notably among EU and ENP countries. Addressing the perspective of different pillars and societal challenges, a broad group of BILAT, INCONET, ERANET and INCO projects exchanged in plenary and parallel sessions how to foster the discussion on how to increase the international participation in H2020. The R2I Cluster of Eastern European and Mediterranean projects, to which RERAM belongs, shared their experiences and recommendations for future collaboration schemes.

2.2.8 Kick-off meeting of FUNES Project

Date, venue, host, website

3-4/12/2014, Paterna, Spain

AIDIMA - Furniture new European skills 2020 (FUNES project)
<http://www.funesproject.eu/>

Participants

The kick-off meeting was attended by the project consortium partners from five countries, i.e. Spain, Italy, Portugal, Belgium, and Poland.

RERAM representative: ITD (Prof. dr. hab. Ewa Ratajczak), InnovaWood (G. Verhaeghe)

Main topics and outcomes

The goal of the project is to develop models of new skills necessary in modern furniture industry. To obtain this goal the following actions will be executed within the project:

- identification of development scenarios for the furniture industry companies,
- analysis of new skills necessary for present and future employees,
- development of training modules (together with appropriate materials) using an Internet platform to facilitate the acquirement of new skills in furniture industry.

The project will be carried out in the period 2014-2017 and is co-financed by the EU funds under the programme ERASMUS+/KA2-Cooperation and Innovation for Good Practices [source: WTI].

RERAM was presented by Prof. dr. hab. Ewa Ratajczak (ITD).

2.2.9 ener2i Brokerage event

Date, venue, host, website

10-11/12/2014, Academy of Sciences of Moldova,
1 Stefan cel Mare bd, Chisinau, Moldova

Event review and documentation of the ener2i energy workshop and the brokerage:
<http://ener2i.eu/object/news/54> , <http://ener2i.eu/object/news/53>

Participants

Event organised by the ener2i partners Agency for Innovation and Technology Transfer (AITT) and Organization for Small and Medium Enterprises Sector Development (ODIMM) and gathered together 56 participants from Moldova, Georgia and several EU countries.

RERAM representatives: UNFU (O. Kiyko), HCS (R. Oberwimmer), AITT (V. Iatchevici, R Chirca)

Main topics and outcomes

Experts of the RERAM team participated in a joint event organized by the partner project ener2i and held a dedicated training session for Moldovan woodworking SMEs about 'Resource and energy efficiency in the forest-based sector of ENP countries'. The brokerage event and energy workshop took place as part of the Top Innovation Event, organised by the Moldovan AITT - Agency for Innovation and Technology Transfer, which is also a partner in RERAM. The Top Innovation Event is the largest and most popular annual event on innovation in Moldova, held at the Academy of Sciences in Chisinau.

The RERAM R2I session of the energy workshop and introduced the participating SMEs to RERAM's Enterprise Check. It provided an overview of tangible solutions to improve efficiency management in wood industries, notably with a focus on solid wood in furniture.

Presentation Prof. Kiyko

https://ener2i.eu/object/news/54/attach/RERAM_introduction_presentation_Orest_Kiyko.pdf

Presentation Mr. R. Oberwimmer

https://ener2i.eu/object/news/54/attach/Moldova_Workshop_Oberwimmer.pdf

2.2.10 Meeting with representatives of the Ministry of the Environment and General Directorate of State Forests

Date, venue, host, website

13/11/2014, Warsaw, Poland

Ministry of the Environment, Department of Forestry and Nature Conservation

<https://www.mos.gov.pl/en>

The State Forests National Forest Holding

<http://www.lasy.gov.pl/publikacje/in-english>

Participants

8 representatives of the Ministry of the Environment and General Directorate of State Forests.

RERAM representative: ITD / Gabriela Bidzińska

Main topics and outcomes

The Meeting concerned the acceptance of WTI's work entitled: Monitoring of the changes in the Polish forest-wood sector according to the standards of the Committee on Forest and the Forest Industry UN ECE/FAO.

RERAM was presented by Gabriela Bidzińska (ITD, Wood Industry Economics Department). The goals of the project and actions planned within the project framework were presented to the decision-making bodies, including the Ministry of the Environment and the representatives of General Directorate of State Forests.

2.3 R2I Dialogue events in 2015

2.3.1 RERAM Roundtable Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine

Date, venue, host, website

24/03/2015

Conference Hall, 22 Harbarska street, 8th floor, Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine

WPFC, www.domv.lviv.ua/reram-round-table

Participants

Businesses, cluster organizations, business development agencies / councils, Regional State Administrations, Ivano-Frankivsk Regional Forestry and Hunting Administrations.

Main topics and outcomes

WPFC presented developments regarding the strategic changes in the forest sector of Ukraine, presented the main tools to increase energy and resource efficiency in woodworking enterprises, heard proposals for filling wood and online maps with its new curriculum WPFC Training Center and project RERAM. At the round table in Ivano-Frankivsk has demonstrated the acute shortage of resources for the effective operation of enterprises, in particular financial and knowledge, and the low competitiveness of domestic products.

2.3.2 Business meeting “International Contact Days” in Ukraine

Date, venue, host, website

26/03/2015

Transcarpathia Chamber of Commerce and Industry

<http://www.tpp.uzhgorod.ua/ukr/page-477.html>

Participants

At the invitation of Vice President of CCI Ukraine, Transcarpathian CCI President, Chairman of the Chamber Carpathian region, the Honorary Consul of the Czech Republic in Uzhgorod Otto Kovchara international business events attended by consuls Consulate General of Poland in Lviv Marian Orlikovski and the Consulate General of Hungary Uzhgorod Ferenc Varga, director of the Hungarian Ukrainian Chamber of Commerce György Cota, head of the Austrian trade office in Lviv Hope Bogatyrenko. Transcarpathian Regional Forestry and Hunting Management was represented by Deputy Vasyl Kyi. From the Department of Economic Development and Trade Zakarpattya Oblast State Administration talked with entrepreneurs Deputy Head of Galina Rusnak trade.

RERAM representative: FORZA

Main topics and outcomes

Networking of representatives of Uzhgorod forest and wood processing industry in Austria, Estonia, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Hungary, Czech Republic, and Zaporizhia, Kyiv, Lviv, Ternopil , Khmel'nitsky and Transcarpathian regions of Ukraine.

2.3.3 Eastern Partnership Panel on Research and Innovation

Date, venue, host, website

26/03/2015

Crowne Plaza Hotel 3, Rue Gineste 1210 BRUSSELS, Belgium
European Commission, European Union External Action

Participants

EC officials, EaP RTD stakeholders, FP7-INCO R2I project coordinators

RERAM representative: IIWH (U. Kies)

Main topics and outcomes

EaP recent developments/ Preparation of the Riga Summit

Research and innovation cooperation: progress since the last Panel meeting

- EaP participation in H2020,
- EaP SICA Call-Assessment and Clustering Workshop
- EaP participation in H2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions

Cooperation on e-infrastructures: E@PConnect

INCONET EaP

EVAL-INNO initiative

R2I projects presentations

2.3.4 RERAM Roundtable Lviv, Ukraine

Date, venue, host, website

30/03/2015

Hotel "George", Pl. Mickiewicza 1, 1st floor, Lviv, Ukraine

WPFC, www.domv.lviv.ua/reram-round-table

Participants

Businesses, cluster organizations, business development agencies / councils, Regional State Administrations, experts.

Main topics and outcomes

WPFC were presented developments regarding the strategic changes in the forest sector of Ukraine, presented the main tools to increase energy and resource efficiency in woodworking enterprises, heard proposals for filling wood and online maps with its new curriculum WPFC Training Center and project RERAM. The main issues discussed at the roundtable in Lviv became the skills, the negative impact of the economic situation in the country, expensive loans and the lack of data on the use of forest raw materials, lack of knowledge on the use of waste products with maximum added value.

2.3.5 RERAM Roundtable Rivne, Ukraine

Date, venue, host, website

31/03/2015

National University of Water and Environment, Conference Hall, 11 Cathedral street, 1st floor, Rivne, Ukraine

WPFC, www.domv.lviv.ua/reram-round-table

Participants

Businesses, cluster organizations, business development agencies / councils, Regional State Administrations, Rivne Regional Forestry and Hunting Administrations, State Forestry.

Main topics and outcomes

WPFC has presented developments regarding the strategic changes in the forest sector of Ukraine, presented the main tools to increase energy and resource efficiency in woodworking enterprises, facilitated discussion on challenges faced by the wood processing industry in regards to resource efficiency. In Rivne, the roundtable participants expressed concerns regarding the ineffective state agencies (lack of coherent policy in the sector overall), out-dated assets of state enterprises and inadequate funding of their activities, poor design Ukrainian production from wood, which makes it difficult to compete with imported analogues, low domestic market for timber and goods wood, furniture, toys, wooden houses.

2.3.6 AFET-ITRE Conference ‘Building together a knowledge-oriented and forward-looking EU Neighbourhood’ in the European Parliament

Date, venue, host, website

31/03/2015, European Parliament, JAN2Q2, Brussels, Belgium

Videostream: <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/news-room/content/20150326IPR38596/html/Committee-on-Foreign-Affairs-meeting-31032015-09.00-12.30>

Photos:

<http://audiovisual.europarl.europa.eu/Package.aspx?id=21723&p=1>

Participants

RERAM representatives: IIWH (Dr. U. Kies), FORZA (Mrs. R. Ustych)

Main topics and outcomes

The event was organized jointly by the European Commission DG Research & Innovation and the European Parliament's Foreign Affairs and Industry, Technology, Research and Energy committees. It was opened by the Chairs of both committees, Elmar Brok and Jerzy Buzek, together with EU Commissioner, Carlos Moedas, and the Latvian Minister for Education and Science, Marite Seile. The conference showcased a number of examples for successful collaboration of European and ENP countries in the EC 7th framework programme. Agenda: www.reram.eu/pdf_files/press_en/2015-03-31_ep_agenda_enp_rtd.pdf

The RERAM project was invited to present its success story in the European Parliament. Mrs. Radmila Ustych of FORZA NGO and Dr. Uwe Kies of IIWH presented together the objectives and first lessons learnt of RERM's trainers programme and enterprise checks in Ukraine. www.reram.eu/pdf_files/press_en/2015-03-31_reram_presentation_ep_kies_ustych.pdf

2.3.7 Joint UNECE-FAO/RERAM Event 'Capacity building for Sustainable Forest Management and Resource Efficiency in the Caucasus and Central Asia'

Date, venue, host, website

23/04/2015, Hotel, Koste, Tbilisi, Georgia

The event was co-organized by RERAM together with the UNECE-FAO ENP Capacity Building project, which addresses the seven target countries Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Uzbekistan.

www.reram.eu/outputs/events/joint-unece-faoreram-event-georgia-23-apr-2015.html

<http://www.unece.org/index.php?id=37795#/>

Participants

The UNECE-FAO Timber Committee and the RERAM consortium organized a joint event in Tbilisi/Georgia, to provide a platform for networking and exchange among initiatives and stakeholders in the region. 40 experts from 18 countries participated in the event.

All partners of both consortia attended.

Main topics and outcomes

The joint event maximized interaction between the participants of both projects, with introductory presentations followed by open debate on the challenges, then group analysis leading to tactics to address the challenges which were presented for peer review. The key results of the dedicated team effort comprise a comprehensive SWOT analysis and a list of dedicated recommendations per the three topic lines.

The event addressed key challenges and opportunities to promote enhanced forestry and develops joint recommendations for forest-based policy and sector initiatives to increase the supply of sustainably produced forest products in the Caucasus and Central Asia region.

- Sustainable Forest Management (SFM): Forest Resources, Reduced Impact Logging, Non-wood Forest Products (NWFP), Fuelwood, Forest Conservation
- Wood Processing and Products: Resource Use and Energy Efficiency, Cleaner Production, Raw Materials, Solid Wood Products, Vocational Education and Training
- Forest-based Markets: Sector Development, Internationalisation, Cluster Management, Innovation Support, Industrial Policy, Certification, Carbon Markets, Ecotourism

Presentations by RERAM partners:

Uwe Kies. RERAM project general introduction [EN / RU version]

www.reram.eu/pdf_files/press_en/unece-reram_joint_event_2015_reram_iivh_uwe_kies_en.pdf

www.reram.eu/pdf_files/press_en/unece-reram_joint_event_2015_reram_iivh_uwe_kies_ru.pdf

Orest Kiyko. Challenges of Resource Efficiency in Wood Industries – UA perspective.

www.reram.eu/pdf_files/press_en/unece-reram_joint_event_2015_resource_efficiency_prof_orest_kiyko.pdf

Ewa Ratajczak. Challenges of International Forest Products Markets – EU perspective.

www.reram.eu/pdf_files/press_en/unece-reram_joint_event_2015_market_challenges_prof_ewa_ratajczak.pdf

2.3.8 1st Meeting of Furniture Industry Clusters of Greater Poland

Date, venue, host, website

29/04/2015, Poznan, Poland

Greater Poland Clustering Center, *Wielkopolskie Centrum Klasteringu*

<http://www.wielkopolskiklastering.pl>

Participants

About 20 representatives of the furniture industry, sciences and business environment institutions (mostly scientists, producers, students, political decision makers)

RERAM representative: ITD / Magdalena Herbec

Main topics and outcomes

The meeting of the cluster coordinators of the furniture industry, sciences and business environment institutions was focused on integrating and providing assistance to the existing cluster initiatives in the Greater Poland. The aim was to increase the potential of science and technology in the process of developing regional innovation smart specialisation strategy. The activities concentrated mainly on the continuation of work carried out within the established clusters consortium in the region in relation to the intensification of internationalisation activities, etc.

RERAM was presented by Magdalena Herbec (ITD, Wood Industry Economics Department).

2.3.9 National stakeholder roundtable organised by the Ukrainian Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources

Date, venue, host, website

26/05/2015

Hotel Dnepr, Conference hall, Kiev, Ukraine.

Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine

<http://minagro.gov.ua/en/node/15990>

The event was organized by the Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine with the assistance of the European Union and international partners under development of the Strategy for Agriculture and Rural Development 2015 – 2020.

http://econews.bei.org.ua/2015/09/blog-post_30.html

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=U6DOdErrels>

Participants

Representative of the Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine, State Forest Resources Agency of Ukraine, businesses, cluster organizations, business development agencies / councils, industry experts.

RERAM representative: WPFC (Volodymyr Vorobey, Volodymyr Popovych) worked on inputs to the policy paper WG8.3 on a new forestry policy for Ukraine.

Main topics and outcomes

United comprehensive strategy for agriculture and rural development in 2015 – 2020 years has to decide actual needs of the industry. Its overall aim is to increase the competitiveness of agriculture and promote rural development in a sustainable manner in accordance with EU and international standards. This strategy will be provided for the short and medium term and include a detailed action plan for implementation. Strategy development proceed, in particular, through a comprehensive process of consultation with stakeholders, including civil society, businesses and donors and performers of projects which part is carrying out workshops, working meetings and round tables to discuss in expert groups elaborated materials. Proposals were developed with the assistance of the State Forest Resources Agency of Ukraine in management of the Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine.

WPFC proposals: <https://goo.gl/cp70rX>

2.3.10 Roundtable ‘Action Plan for Lviv Regional Forestry Administration’

Date, venue, host, website

28/08/2015

Lviv Regional Forestry Administration, Yavornytsky str. 8b, Lviv, Ukraine

WPFC, www.domv.lviv.ua/measures-for-success-of-lviv-regional-forestry-administration

Participants

WPFC, Hunting Administration Lviv, Ukraine NLTU, enterprises and organizations of business support forest industry in the region, MP of Ukraine Mr. Ostap Yednak, who initiated the meeting, Deputy Head of Lviv Hunting Administration Mr. Anatoliy Deynetsi.

RERAM representative: WPFC (V. Vorobey, V. Popovych), UNFU (O. Kiyko)

Main topics and outcomes

The round table discussed a comprehensive program of introducing a transparent, efficient and effective system of monitoring of forest resources, efficiency analysis and management of forest resources Lviv region.

The main result of the meeting was the agreement to establish a working group to develop terms of reference for improving the mechanism for detecting illegal logging of wood, and on the establishment of the forestry sector, which would be included representatives of wood processing, furniture manufacturing and forestry. They would together decide the question of efficiency of use of forest resources, strategic development of the industry, because, speaking for the forest sector of the region, should be guided not only economic benefits but also social and environmental.

2.3.11 Lisderevmash – National Ukrainian Wood Industry Fair: Innovation workshop at the Wood Invest Forum 2015

Date, venue, host, website

23/09/2015

International Exhibition Centre, Hall No.1, Brovarsky Avenue, 15, Kyiv, Ukraine

Ukrainian association of woodworking companies, State Forest Resources Agency of Ukraine

Web: www.woodinvest.in.ua Agenda: www.woodinvest.in.ua/p/blog-page.html

Results: www.lesovod.org.ua/node/26115

Video: www.youtube.com/watch?v=WStA5mDzzhM

RERAM: www.reram.eu/news/reram-wood-invest-forum-23-sep-2015-kiev-ukraine.html

Participants

Businesses, cluster organizations, business development agencies / councils, People's Deputies, State Forestry, educational institutions, international experts and analysts.

RERAM representatives: UNFU, WPFC, FORZA

Main topics and outcomes

Wood Invest Forum '2015 was the first platform in the forestry sector in Ukraine, created to highlight and discuss issues of forestry and wood processing industry in Ukraine, and aims to become a kind of platform for transparent communication processes in dialogue between "government-business" and "power-investor." The theme of this forum is "Forest and woodworking, reforms, investment, innovations." The event will take place every year in the framework of the international exhibition "Lisderevmash".

Road map: For the near future, a new strategy to a new level of development, threats and prospects of the coming legislative changes for the industry, as well as factors that contribute to the investment attractiveness of the forestry industry, including in the context of the adopted law banning the export of unprocessed wood was discussed by the forestry and wood processing experts.

2.3.12 Seminar Clusterisation and Innovations in the Republic of Moldova

Date, venue, host, website

26/11/2015

Academy of Science of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Participants

Gheorghe Duca, President of the Academy of Sciences of Moldova; Rimantas Latakas, Representative from the Embassy of Lithuania in Moldova; various RTI experts and consultants; public authorities, diplomatic corps, scientists, companies, managers of innovative infrastructure institutions

RERAM representatives: AITT (V. Iatchevici, R. Chirca)

Main topics and outcomes

- Agency for Innovation and Technology Transfer, presentation of mission and projects, including ener2i and RERAM
- Visoriai Information Technology Park
- Moldovan-Lithuanian Cluster
- International business development program DEMOLA

2.3.13 TEEB study for Georgian forest sector: stakeholder meeting

Date, venue, host, website

26-27 November 2015, Batumi, Georgia

ENPI East FLEG by World Bank, WWF, IUCN

<http://www.enpi-fleg.org/news/teeb-study-for-forestry-sector-to-be-conducted-in-ajara-autonomous-republic-georgia/>

Participants

30 participants at the high level round table chaired by Giorgi Sanadiradze, the Director of WWF-Caucasus Programme Office, and Besarion Abashidze, Deputy Minister of Environment and Natural Resources Protection of Georgia

RERAM representative: AUG (M. Khostharia)

Main topics and outcomes

TEEB study for forestry sector to be conducted in Ajara Autonomous Republic, Georgia
The Georgian Government assigns high importance to the TEEB process. In 2013, as a joint effort of the Government of Georgia, United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and WWF-Caucasus, the TEEB Scoping Study for the five key sectors of Georgian economy (including forestry) was produced. We welcome the idea of conducting a full-scale TEEB study for the forestry sector, because we understand how important natural ecosystems are for our country and people. “

TEEB is an international initiative promoting sustainable economies in which the values of biodiversity and ecosystem services are fully reflected in decision-making. TEEB study marks the relationship between the growing loss of biodiversity and ecosystem degradation and the benefits of conservation and sustainable use.

2.3.14 UNECE/FAO-UNDA Balkan workshop on Forest Products Markets and Forest Sector Workforce

Date, venue, host, website

8-10 December 2015, TA Congress for Hotel Nikic,
Kralja Nikole bb, 81000 Podgorica, Montenegro

The workshop was conducted in cooperation with the UNECE/FAO UNDA project on Sustainable Forest Management for Greener Economies in the Caucasus and Central Asia, and supported by the UNECE/FAO Team of Specialists on Forest Products Markets and the joint ILO/UNECE/FAO Team of Specialists on Green Jobs in the Forest Sector.

<http://www.unece.org/index.php?id=41338#/>

Participants

The workshop brought together 20 experts from Albania, Belgium, Croatia, Finland, Ireland, Montenegro, Serbia, The Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia and Ukraine

RERAM representative: UNFU (O. Kiyko)

Main topics and outcomes

The aim was to discuss, exchange experiences, map out the needs for capacity building as well as to formulate recommendations for the future work on forest product markets and forest sector workforce. This meeting gave background information for a UNECE/FAO study paper on forest sector workforce, which will be completed in 2016.

<http://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/timber/workshops/2015/Balkan-workshop-full-programme01122015.pdf>

Prof. Orest Kiyko of UNFU gave a lecture on “Domestic consumption VS exporting: example from Ukrainian forest sector”

<http://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/timber/workshops/2015/7-orest-kiyko-reram-project.pdf>

2.3.15 Eastern Partnership R2I Cluster Meeting

Date, venue, host, website

17/12/2015

European Commission, DG RTD, Square Orban 8, room 7.A149, Brussels, Belgium

Participants

EC DG RTD Project Officers, FP7-INCO R2I project coordinators

RERAM representative: Innovawood (G. Verhaeghe)

Main topics and outcomes

Update on policy developments: EaP regional/bilateral (DG RTD)

INCONET EaP status / upcoming activities (ZSI)

R2I projects presentations: status/upcoming activities; identified opportunities & challenges;
tracks for follow-up

R2I Cluster way forward: possible future activities, policy recommendations

2.3.16 Lviv Wood Processing and Furniture Cluster Forum

Date, venue, host, website

23/12/2015

WPFC, www.domv.lviv.ua/wpfc-forum-2015

Participants

Businesses, cluster organizations, business development agencies / councils, Regional State Administrations, Lviv Regional Forestry and Hunting Administration, State Forestry, educational institutions, international experts and analysts.

RERAM representatives: UNFU (Orest Kiyko), WPFC (V. Vorobey)

Main topics and outcomes

The Forum dealt with two important aspects of the industry - strategic changes in the wood industry and forestry sector and initiatives and innovation in the region. Prof. Orest Kiyko described his vision for forest sector development strategy of the Carpathian region of Ukraine and the possibility of solving existing problems through institutionalization of the forest sector. He identified specific objectives, design and implementation of quality strategy and the introduction of innovative solutions in production and management processes.

The Forum has become a first meeting where a concept of the Lviv Regional Forest Council has been presented to the industry players. A panel discussion was dedicated to the Council, its main goals, possible modus operandi etc.

The outcome of the Forum was the introduction of various forest sector players, the presentation possibilities of cooperation between related associations and woodworking companies, as well as working out plans to strengthen the cooperation of research institutions, business, government, organizations, innovation and the public to improve the use of wood as a resource. The Forum has demonstrated a need for informal meeting points, as networking has continued long after the official end of the event.

2.4 R2I Dialogue events in 2016

2.4.1 Eastern Partnership Panel on Environment and Climate Change

Date, venue, host, website

16/02/2016

Crowne Plaza Hotel, Brussels, Belgium

European Commission, DG ENV & DG NEAR, EEAS

Participants

EaP panel ministerial representatives

RERAM representative: RECC (S. Akhobadze)

Main topics and outcomes

Ad-hoc Meeting to discuss and comment on the Draft Declaration for the Ministerial Meeting on Environment.

Inputs from regional stakeholders on project experiences.

2.4.2 Georgia National Forestry Agency Strategy: Stakeholder Workshop

Date, venue, host, website

27-29/02/2016, Kobuleti, Georgia

CENN Caucasus Environmental NGO Network, coorganized by GIZ

<http://w3.cenn.org/wssl/>

Participants

National NGOs and stakeholders

RERAM representative: AUG (M. Khostaria)

Main topics and outcomes

Inputs to the Draft of the National Forestry Agency of Georgia

2.4.3 Study trip for Ukrainian wood enterprises to Austria

Date, venue, host, website

14-18/03/2016, Graz, Styria region, Austria
Organized and hosted by HCS and FORZA

Participants

Ukrainian group – owners and managers of the enterprises:

- Mebli Styl Furniture factory www.hausmobel.eu www.meblastyle.com
- Gelika furniture factory www.gelika.org
- Krokwood Ltd. <http://krokwood.com.ua/en/>
- Eurostandart Ltd. <http://olles.com.ua/>
- Uzhhorod consulting center www.consulting.uz.ua
- Agroderew Ltd. www.agroderew.com
- Interwoodkommerz Ltd.
- WOODWERK factory <http://woodwerk.com/uk/>
- Buk Holding” Ltd. www.bukholding.com.ua

RERAM representatives: HCS (R. Oberwimmer, E. Schmidt), FORZA (L. Loyko, R. Ustych)

The following companies and institutions were visited:

- Katzbeck Fenster www.katzbeck.at/en
- Abalon Hardwood <http://abalon-hardwood.com/>
- Josef Prödl Tischlerei www.proedl.at/en
- EHP European Hardwood Production www.ehp.at/index.php?id=1&L=1
- Weitzer Parkett www.weitzer-parkett.com/en/
- Kulmer Bau www.kulmerbau.at
- Schloffer Furniture Design <http://www.schloffer.com/index.php?id=7>
- KAPO www.kapo.at
- Landwirtschaftliche Fachschule Güssing (Agricultural College) www.lfsguessing.at

Main goal, activities and main outcomes

Learn about set up of wood processing and furniture production in general, with particular focus on efficient use of raw materials and energy. “An investment in knowledge always pays the best interest”: This quote of Benjamin Franklin, which was pronounced by the director of agricultural college in Güssing, became the theme line of the study tour to wood processing enterprises in Austria.

Note: A detailed report can be found in the deliverable **D3.3 ‘Reality checks and benchmarking’** as well as in Ukrainian language at the FORZA website: <http://www.forza.org.ua/uk/reram/investiciyi-v-znannya-zavzhdi-dayut-naybilshiy-pributok>

2.4.4 Parliament of Georgia, Environmental Protection and Natural Resources Committee, Working Meeting about the Forest Code

Date, venue, host, website

24/04/2016

Parliament of Georgia, Tbilisi, Georgia

<http://www.parliament.ge/en/saparlamento-saqmianoba/komitetebi/garemos-dacvisa-da-bunebrivi-resursebis-komiteti/axali-ambebi-garemo/garemos-dacvisa-da-bunebrivi-resursebis-komitetshi-tyis-kodeqsis-proeqttan-dakavshirebit-samushao-shexvedra-gaimarta.page>

Participants

RERAM representatives: AUG (T. Kandelaki)

Main topics and outcomes

The Committee held the preliminary consideration of the draft Forest Code. The meeting was chaired by Gia Zhorzholiani and attended by the representatives of the National Forest Agency, Academy of Sciences and Patriarchy of Georgia. The Committee started considerations on forest reform in February when the Head of Foreign Policy Department of the Environmental Ministry, Karlo Amirgulashvili introduced the working draft of the Code. As he stated, the draft was further considered in various regions with participation of the local population and field specialists. The draft gained positive evaluation. The fundamental line of the Code is substitution of the social cut practice with economy function. The new Code will fundamentally change legal relations in forest sphere and eliminate gaps in the law. One of the authors, Merab Dvali made additional elucidations and answered the questions. Hence, the Forest Management Agency shall regain economy function. The draft defines new types of forest usage and relevant procedures. The new Code does not envisage issue of new licenses and defines new rules of regulation of so-called “expulsion” and new borders. The draft envisages new systems of forest registration. The forests will be as state so municipal and private. Regardless of forest types, management will be based on strictly outlined plans. The participants expressed common opinion that forest protection and maintenance of biologic diversity is necessary but implementation achievements were different. The Chair hoped that the working meetings will further be held to finalize the draft.

2.4.5 LUKE Symposium on Wood Products Industries in Future Bioeconomy Business

Date, venue, host, website

07-08/04/2016

LUKE National Resources Institute Finland, Lahti, Finland

www.metla.fi/tapahtumat/2016/rdisymposium/

Participants

Ca. 90 international researchers and industry representatives from all over Europe and USA

RERAM representatives: UNFU (O. Kiyko), InnovaWood (G. Verhaeghe)

Main topics and outcomes

Symposium highlights: the importance of industries in wood products cluster in the European bio-economy (sawn timber, wood panels, furniture, wood construction, wood packaging, machine manufacturing, etc.); new opportunities for business, markets, products, services and wood design; implications of and effects to EU-strategic processes; networking at the European level between decision makers of wood products industries, society, policy and research funding

The first day consists of presentations given by leading European bio-economy experts, followed by interactive panel discussions, where the audience can challenge the speakers. In the business forum, the participants will get familiar with a selection of innovative company solutions through flash presentations and small-group discussions.

In the second day, the participants are invited to discuss, plan, and network to produce ideas for further collaborative actions. Excursion includes a visit to a wooden building element manufacturer to learn how woodworking industries take quick steps towards modern multi-storey timber construction markets.

The event represented an excellent international networking opportunity for the Ukrainian research group at UNFU (see attached travel report of Prof. O. Kiyko).

2.4.6 RERAM Resource Efficiency Workshop & Training in Georgia

Date, venue, host, website

19-20/04/2016

Environmental Information and Education Centre, Chavchavadze Ave.N76/c, Tbilisi, Georgia

Organized and hosted by RECC and AUG

Participants

Mr. Karlo Amirgulshvili, Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources Protection of Georgia, Head of the Forest policy Department

Malkhaz Adeishvili, UNIDO's Resource Effective and Cleaner Production Resource Effective and Cleaner Production Demonstrational, project coordinator

Wood industry managers

RERAM representatives: HCS (R. Oberwimmer, C. Angerbauer, V. Jurnjak), RECC (S. Akhobadze), AUG (T. Kandelaki, M. Khostharia)

Main topics and outcomes

RERAM is concentrated on small and medium woodworking enterprises that in general have non-effective use of raw materials. The companies will see benefit from educational efficiency inspections, training activities, subsequently the general awareness will improve in the companies which will result in a demonstrational practice examples in sustainable use of raw materials. Wide public awareness and cooperation in ENP countries will further advance the inner growth potential in the field of wood resources. Resource efficiency is always important for companies as well as the environment.

At the workshop, the members held a number of presentations in which they discussed their findings and comments, after which there was a free discussion on some of the problems and necessities as well as what progress had be made as a result of the former recommendations. Further steps and measures were planned at the end of the meeting as well as a reach of understanding for further cooperation between the companies for assurance of resource and energy efficiency.

2.4.7 UNIDO RECP Trainings for national experts in Georgia

Date, venue, host

26-27/04/2016, Energy Efficiency Center Georgia (EEC), Tbilisi, Georgia

Previous dates: 11-14/12/2015, 29-30/06/2015, 4/6/2015

UNIDO RECP Project

<http://recp.ge/?cat=11>

Participants

National industry experts; international experts as trainers

RERAM representatives: AUG (T. Kandelaki, M. Khostharia)

Main topics and outcomes

The training covered first six modules of the RECP course including the following: RECP concept and Practice; RECP assessment; Motivation, Commitment and Team; RECP baseline and indicators; Initial assessment; Detailed assessment.

National experts passed a test in RECP methodology and technique.

Following the classroom training the national experts visited selected demonstration companies for introducing themselves to the companies' managements and undertaking first RECP observations in the enterprises. The national experts were coached by the International Expert and the project National Coordinator during the visits.

The national experts presented the results of RECP assessments undertaken in selected companies, including the RECP indicators (resource use, environmental pollution, product output, resource intensity, and pollution intensity), opportunities for improving the resource use efficiency, economic and environmental performance of the companies.

2.4.8 RERAM conference in Georgia 'Efficient and sustainable use of resources in forestry sector'

Date, venue, host

06/05/2016

AUG, David Agmashenebeli Alley 240, auditorium 200, Tbilisi, Georgia

Organized and hosted by AUG

https://www.facebook.com/AgrUni/photos/?tab=album&album_id=1019225174780229

Participants

Georgian ministries, enterprises, researchers, experts, banks, NGOs

RERAM representatives: AUG (T. Kandelaki, M. Khostharia), RECC (S. Akhobadze)

Main topics and outcomes

Presentation of RERAM project results and lessons learnt

Science and industry: obvious examples of relations

Futures research needs in the forestry wood value chain domain

2.4.9 RERAM Final Conference in Lviv, Ukraine

Date, venue, host, website

18-19/05/2016

Hotel Taurus, Lviv, Ukraine

Organized and hosted by IIWH, FORZA, UNFU, WPFC

www.reram.eu

Participants

87 participants from wood processing enterprises, business support organizations, research and consulting organizations from the forest-based sector. In total 35 Ukrainian companies and 12 companies from other ENP and EU countries participated.

The whole RERAM consortium was present.

Main topics and outcomes

The RERAM final conference offered an international platform for networking and exchange among businesses and stakeholders in the European Neighbourhood Eastern Partnership region (ENP-EaP). The main goal was to present and debate tangible solutions that can foster efficient use of raw materials and resources for a more competitive forest-based sector in ENP countries. Practical approaches and tools for small and medium enterprises to improve resource efficiency and cleaner production in woodworking were demonstrated and discussed. Three panel discussions with woodworking companies and experts provided a vital forum to showcase and debate these efficiency solutions and new ways to improve business performance and innovation in the ENP-EaP region.

Note: The RERAM final event is fully documented in its own deliverable report **D6.4** ‘Conference Proceedings’ and on the project website www.reram.eu .

2.4.10 Eastern Partnership Panel on Environment and Climate Change

Date, venue, host

26-27/05/2016

Crowne Plaza Hotel, Brussels, Belgium

European Commission, DG ENV & DG NEAR, EEAS

Participants

EaP panel ministerial representatives

RERAM representative: RECC (S. Akhobadze)

Main topics and outcomes

Multi-stakeholders meeting – exchange of views on EU and EaP environment Ministers meeting, Luxembourg, October 2016

Opinions of stakeholders: NGOs, IFIs and international organisations on the Ministerial meeting and Declaration; Programmes and financial assistance for the EaP region; Circular Economy Package; After COP21; Capacity building of NGOs in the Eastern Partnership; Revised work programme for Platform 2 – role and tasks.

2.4.11 RECC side event at the UNECE 8th Ministerial Conference in Batumi

Note: This event took place after the official end of the RERAM project. No costs were claimed on the project.

Date, venue, host, website

10/06/2016

Side event at the UNECE Environment for Europe Conference, Hilton Hotel, Batumi, Georgia

www.rec-caucasus.org/n.php?id=1465911735&lang=en

Participants

Ca. 50 international forest policy experts

RERAM representatives: RECC (S. Akhobadze), AUG (T. Kandelaki, M. Khostharia)

Main topics and outcomes

Title: Mainstreaming practical application of green development mechanisms into environmental policies and practice in South Caucasus

The side event was opened by the RECC Director Sophiko Akhobadze and the Deputy Minister of Nature Protection of the Republic of Armenia Mr. Khachik Hakobyan, which was followed by the presentation of the director Ms Malak Shukurova regarding the Commitment of REC Caucasus to Batumi Initiative on Green Economy (BIG-E).

The following projects were presented at the side event:

- “Fostering Community Biodiversity Conservation Policy and Practices in Mountain Regions of the South Caucasus” – presented by Mr. Rubik Shahazizyan and Mr. Bariz Mehdiyev
- “Support Development of Biodiversity Conservation Policies and Practices in Mountain Regions of the South Caucasus” – presented by Ms. Tatiana Danielyan
- “Mainstreaming the Payment for Ecosystem Services for Green Growth in South Caucasus” – Presented by Mr. Bariz Mehdiyev
- RERAM “Strengthen Cleaner Production Policy and Practice in the South Caucasus Countries through Applying Integrated and Preventive Environmental Strategy” – presented by Mr. Teimuraz Kandelaki
- RECP “Resource Efficiency and Cleaner Production”

REC Caucasus being a flagman and propagator of Green Economy and Green Development in the region is committed to the objectives and priorities of the EFE process. Bearing in mind that one of the theme of the Eighth EFE Ministerial Conference is “Greening The Economy in the Pan-European Region” we believe that outputs of the above mentioned projects implemented by REC Caucasus, which is going to be presented during side event will contribute to the major ideas and goals of the conference.

Impressions

3. Annex: Agendas and Participants Lists

(not included in public version published on www.reram.eu)

Citation, Acknowledgement and Disclaimer

Kies U., Oberwimmer R., Vorobey V., 2016.
R2I Research-to-Innovation Dialogues. RERAM project report D4.2.
Internationales Institut für Wald und Holz e.V., Holzcluster Steiermark GmbH,
Wood Processing and Furniture Cluster. Münster, Graz, Lviv.
www.reram.eu

The RERAM project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme (FP7 2007-2013) under the grant agreement n°609573 from 01/06/2014 to 31/05/2016. The content of the document reflects only the authors' views. The European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

